

Remote Real-time Research Platform for Control Engineering

Fariba Moghaddam¹[0000-0001-6800-7776] and Maël Forestal¹[0000-0003-1245-8783]

¹ University of Applied Sciences and Arts Western Switzerland, 1950 Sion, Switzerland

Abstract. A classical remote labs platform is upgraded to develop and implement advanced remote real-time tools for research activities through a collaborative network, deploying distant equipment in electrical, mechanical and control engineering. The Web-based collaborative digital platform offers different issues such as secure Web access and data transfer with no required third-party software or licenses, remote access for controlling and monitoring of research equipment, user-friendly Web interface with live video and data acquisition, fluid data visualization allowing time plots with logging features, full system security as well as digital tools such as data sharing, data processing and data saving. In addition, the Web interface proposes a textual programming environment and code sharing tools for distance programming of research equipment, not locally available. The remote platform helps to build less infrastructure and to share more of the existing equipment. Furthermore, it allows to concentrate on developing rich collaborative applications and to offer further synergies between universities and industrial partners.

Keywords: Remote tools, Distance programming, Online monitoring.

1 Introduction

Experimental research plays an important role in the originality of research in engineering. However, the system set up for research implementation needs advanced tools, costly equipment and machinery with large investment that only a limited number of institutions can afford. With the advent of IoT (Internet of Things), one requires more access to the remote infrastructure to be able to do distance programming, data visualization, system monitoring and algorithm implementation. Currently, apart from some expensive proprietary ecosystems that are not meant for being embedded in small-scale systems for research applications, no real open solution exists.

The existing remote labs platforms designed for education issues are not always suitable to carry out research activities in a free and widespread way, due to some limitations in data communication or the user interface. For example, the students' interactions with remote equipment are often limited to change only the system configuration, the controller parameters, the setpoints and to collect and analyze the data on their computer. This work proposes to improve the user Web-based interface of the existing

remote platform at University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland, used for education [1], [2], by adding a new textual programming environment and code sharing tools through Web browser.

Fig. 1. Remote digital collaborative platform for engineering applications.

2 Infrastructure

The proposed infrastructure is composed of:

- 1) Laboratory devices fully equipped with different sensors, actuators and real-time embedded controllers. MyRIO and CompactRIO controllers of National Instruments are used with FPGA and CPU modules, IO modules and Ethernet connection allowing remote operations as well as live video streaming. As test infrastructure, a pool of several laboratory equipment is available such as electrical motors, robots, moveable photovoltaic panels for sun tracking or other didactic lab experiments.
- 2) A common gateway interface offering standard telecommunication protocols (WebSocket) with secure data transmission between the local infrastructure and the remote users/programmers [3]. Communication between the Web interface and the remote system and the local controller includes real-time communication channels for operations such as start/stop the system, real-time data visualization, send commands as well as algorithms to be transferred in terms of source code.
- 3) A lab server for monitoring the system access and usage history to be aware of the connected devices which should be reached behind firewalls and without custom network configuration.
- 4) A Web-based Interface offering online control and monitoring panel which connects the users/programmers to the remote infrastructure. The Web interface proposes a user-friendly interface with live video streaming of the test site and data acquisition. It allows users to monitor the lab equipment, send commands and write algorithms in a textual programming language such as Python.
- 5) Remote interactive tools to implement services such as:
 - Data sharing, data processing and data saving

- Real-time signal processing
- Remote textual programming and code sharing
- Distance programming of lab equipment
- Remote monitoring and data visualization
- Advanced system modeling and control algorithms development

Fig. 2. Remote infrastructure composed of lab devices and local controllers, bidirectional data transfer, lab server, Web-based interface offering different interactive digital tools.

Figure 2 shows the overall infrastructure of the developed collaborative remote platform with a Web-based SPA (Single Page Application) offering data visualization, live video streaming, programming environment and control of the remote devices by using local controllers.

3 Communication and security aspects

In remote engineering, communication protocols are open and give the freedom to develop innovative solutions. Learning platforms are not standardized to a level which would permit an easy migration. This is why for our remote experimentation setup, effort has been put mostly on the remote experiment and client-side tools with data under the direct control of the client rather than based on cloud storage.

The connection between the remote users and the server connected to the lab experiments must be secured against malevolent actors. The lab experiments and the server computer must be protected against unauthorized connection attempts which could steal resources, impair their usage by the users they are destined to, and possibly damage them by submitting repeated extreme commands. Also, the user computers should be protected against malware, phishing attempts, or any content which would tarnish the lab institution. And the experimental data integrity should be guaranteed to ensure users can rely on their remote experiment outcome.

On the remote lab side, server is connected to wired network which is difficult to attack. The weakest side is the client computers and their Internet access: Wi-fi connections have become the norm on laptops and tablets, and the security of public Wi-fi access points is often low or impossible to assess. To improve overall security, the use of TLS (SSL) encryption has become prevalent (HTTPS URLs), with more and more restrictions enforced to discourage practices known to be easily abused. Modern browsers flag pages served without encryption as unsecure, refuse unencrypted auxiliary resources accessed from encrypted pages (“mixed content”), and remember if a site has been served via HTTPS to not switch back to unencrypted HTTP in future accesses (“HTTP Strict-Transport-Security”). Cross-origin constraints restrict possible implementations further (cross-origin refers to web content in the same page obtained from different servers). The different digital tools are served from a server implemented in LabVIEW to the users’ browsers via HTTP (a simple request/reply protocol where the connection is closed after one or a few requests) and WebSocket [3], a lasting bidirectional stream of messages starting with an HTTP handshake. Both are supported natively by browsers. For the reasons described above, the encrypted versions of these protocols are used: HTTPS and WSS [2]. On WebSocket, messages are encoded in JSON [4], a good compromise between legibility and conciseness which is supported natively in browsers and elsewhere.

4 Interactive tools

With the evolution of technologies involved in remote experiments, the remote environment and digital tools have changed very significantly. On the remote user side, mostly for security reasons, Java applets, Flash Player applications, and other native browser plugins have been replaced by JavaScript web applications.

Fig. 3. Web-based control and monitoring panels of smart devices in Open-Loop and Closed-loop modes.

As shown in figure 3, different interactive tools are proposed in a web-based user interface to avoid any installation for the remote users [1]. The Front-End interface allows the following features:

- Device On/Off
- Open-loop mode
- Closed-loop mode with choice of controllers (PID, State-space control, ...)
- Control and monitoring of system inputs (setpoints, controller parameters)
- Data visualization and saving
- Webcam live video

To transfer the control algorithms towards the device controller, in terms of source code, the HTML interface has been upgraded. The following sections present the developed remote programming environment and code sharing tools for distance programming of lab equipment as well as data acquisition and monitoring interface of the remote infrastructure.

4.1 Remote programming and code sharing

The HTML interface allows algorithms programming by means of a textual code editor. As our lab devices are equipped by the National Instruments controllers (MyRIO, CRIO), the code inserted in the Web interface must be only in the Python programming language. Nowadays, the Python language is progressively used for system scripting, Web development as well as software and algorithms development.

To achieve this aim, the method “SendPythonScript” has been developed in order to create a .py file and to paste the Python source code in it. This method calls the LabVIEW VI “System Exec” to compile and execute the Python code, directly on the National Instruments controllers. The LabVIEW VI “System Exec” needs the name of the file with the .py extension to compile and run the Python source code. The final file is executed on the Real-time Linux operation system.

Consequently, other programming languages such as C or Matlab should be first converted to Python, before inserting in the code editor. For this purpose, different converters such as SMOP (Simple Matlab/Octave to Python) or many other C to Python converters may be used.

Figure 4 shows the five steps to follow in the Web interface to upload code on the National Instrument controllers, by using a simple code editor. After selecting the “Programming” Tab (1) and clicking on the button “Edit” (2), a Pop-up window appears for inserting the code script in Python (3). Few seconds after uploading the code (4) on the remote controller, the programming environment provides feedbacks such as compilation status, errors or warnings, or results of calculation (5).

Fig. 4. Web-based user interface for distance programming.

Once the Python code is inserted in the Pop-up window, the following steps are undertaken:

- I. Splitting the script inserted in the Pop-up to several substring of maximum 500 characters each.
- II. Sending the characters frames through TCP/IP.
- III. Receiving the frames by Lab Server and sending them to the controller (MyRIO, CRIO) using JSON format.
- IV. Using the developed method “SendPythonScript” to create a .py file and to paste the Python source code in it. This method calls the LabVIEW VI “System Exec” to compile and execute the Python source code. The final file is executed on the Real-time Linux operation system.
- V. Compiling the Python file and sending compilation status, errors or warnings.
- VI. Using a bidirectional Socket communication for variable transfer between Python and LabVIEW. “CRIO to Python” is used to forward the real measurements to Python and to transfer them to the remote user. “Python to CRIO” is used to send the parameters and commands from the remote user to the controller. To ensure a high-speed data acquisition with the Hardware, the FPGA module of the controller is used.

It takes between 1 to 3 seconds to transfer and compile the code and receive the compilation status on the Web interface (steps I to VI). A sampling period of 2 to 3 milliseconds is required, for example to run the Python source code of a PID controller on the CPU. The sampling period may be reduced by using a more efficient and faster processor or by optimizing the algorithms.

4.2 Remote monitoring and data acquisition

In addition to telemetry monitoring, commands and parameters sending, algorithms programming in a textual language such as Python, the Web-based interface allows the data visualization of the remote infrastructure as well as a live video.

Control parameters and measurement data are sent as numbers and the video stream is sent as JPEG images in the same HTML interface, the easiest way to ensure synchronization between video and real-time signal traces. The image transmission rate is 10 images per second. As for the data transmission rate, the data packages of 200 numbers, with acquisition rate of 500 microseconds, are sent every 100 milliseconds. Based on these data and images rates, the video quality suits well its purpose as a direct way to assess the system functioning.

5 Experimental results

A state-space control system is implemented for controlling the position of a ball on a rail, by means of a speed observer. Figure 5 shows a ball system with an optical position sensor and a servomotor for moving a rail.

Fig. 5. Lab experiment to control the position of a ball on a rail, using an optical sensor and a servomotor.

The system can be described by the following nonlinear differential equation, where m is the mass of the ball, R its radius and J its inertia:

$$\left(\frac{J}{R^2} + m\right)\ddot{r} - mg\sin(\alpha) - mR\dot{\alpha}^2 = 0 \quad (1)$$

The variable r is the position of the ball to be controlled and the variable α is the angle of rotation of the rail around its center of gravity.

After the linearization of the equation (1), the state-space model can be described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\underline{x}} &= \underline{A} \underline{x} + \underline{B} u \\ \underline{y} &= \underline{C} \underline{x} + \underline{D} u\end{aligned}$$

$$\dot{\underline{x}} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{r} \\ \ddot{r} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} r \\ \dot{r} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{mg}{\frac{J}{R^2} + m} \end{bmatrix} \alpha \quad (2)$$

$$\underline{y} = r = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} r \\ \dot{r} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \end{bmatrix} \alpha$$

Where \dot{r} is the speed of the moving ball to be observed by an observer. Thus, the observed variables included in the state vector \underline{x} are position r and speed \dot{r} .

The Simulink block diagram in figure 6 presents the state-space position controller and the speed observer which have been implemented as Python code in the Web-based programming environment.

The parameters of the state-space controller $\underline{K} = [K_1, K_2, K_3]$ and the parameters of the observer $\underline{F} = [F_1, F_2]$ have been calculated by the pole placement method.

Fig. 6. Simulink bloc diagram of the state-space position controller and the speed observer.

The following parameters are sent through the code editor of figure 4: the position setpoint, the parameters of the state-space controller $\underline{K} = [K_1, K_2, K_3]$, the parameters of the speed observer $\underline{F} = [F_1, F_2]$. In addition, the Python source code of the state-space position controller and the speed observer are transferred to the remote controller as described in section 4.1.

In return, different real-time signals such as the position measurement in millimeters and the rail angle in degrees as well as a live video streaming are received (see Figure 7).

The time to transfer and compile the code and receive the compilation status is about 3 seconds. A sampling period of 3 milliseconds is required, to run the Python code of the state-space controller and its observer on the CPU.

Fig. 6. Data visualization integrated in the Web-based interface, with example of the state-space position control of a ball system.

6 Conclusion

The increasing use of Information and Communication Technologies had, has, and will have various impacts on academic institutions, the daily work of researchers, the scientific publication and the substance of research. Currently, the remote research methodologies have limited options, but as more users utilize the remote possibilities, the knowledge and technology around remote methods will improve [5], [6]. This will empower more digital skills, faster et more reliable telecommunication services as well as new programs and applications with a better understanding of their characteristics.

This work promotes different issues through a Web-based collaborative digital platform with low requirements for deployment and operation: secure Web access and data transfer with no required third-party software or licenses, remote access for controlling and monitoring of research equipment, user-friendly Web interface with live video and data acquisition, fluid data visualization allowing time plots with logging features, full system security, digital tools such as data sharing, data processing and data saving,

textual Web programming environment and code sharing tools for distance programming of lab equipment.

Furthermore, the idea to expand and improve research in engineering fields by providing remote access to infrastructure, equipment, resources and data leads to substantial benefits for science and economy [7]. In fact, the developed remote platform offers the engineers and researchers to share their experience, expertise and resources as well as to connect and to collaborate more efficiently, a key characteristic of science literacy. As for economic impact, one can mention reducing costs of laboratories and research equipment in higher education by sharing the available infrastructure, resources and equipment for use in engineering fields.

References

1. F. Moghaddam, A. Vaccari, T. Moniquet, C. Salzmann, Y. Piguat, S. Saab, R. Jaafar, A. Suratgar, Q. Shafiee, N. Dan Lamso, H. Alzouma Mayaki, H. Ali Barkad, H. Saliyah Hassane and D. Gillet: Massive Open Online Labs (MOOLs) - An Innovative Solution to Achieving SDGs in the Global South. Exp.at 2019 – 5th Experiment International Conference, Portugal (2019).
2. F. Moghaddam, A. Vaccari, Ch. Salzmann, Y. Piguat and D. Gillet: Interactive Lab Experimentation and Simulation Tools for Remote Laboratories. REV2021 – 18th International Conference on Remote Engineering and Virtual Instrumentation, (2021).
3. RFC6455 - The WebSocket Protocol : <http://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc6455>
4. RFC8259 - The JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) : <https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc8259>
5. M. Yan, R. Filieri and M. Gorton: Continuance intention of online technologies, a systematic literature review, International Journal of Information Management, Vol. 58, (2021).
6. H. Saliyah-Hassane, M. Castro Gil, D. Gillet, M.L. Petrie, J.B. Da Silva, L.P. Zapata Rivera, L. Mellos Carlos, J. W. Shockley, J. Zalewski, G.R. Alves and E. Sancristobal Ruiz: Online Laboratories in Engineering Education: Innovation, Disruption, and Future Potential, Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Teaching, Assessment, and Learning for Engineering, (2019).
7. N. Roztocki, P. Soja and H.R. Weistroffer: The role of information and communication technologies in socioeconomic development, towards a multi-dimensional framework, Information Technology for Development, Vol. 25, (2019).